
238. Ophiion: a most curious cluster

THE recent study entitled ‘*Gaia Net: Toward Robust Spectroscopic Parameters of Stars of all Evolutionary Stages*’, by Huson et al. (2025), reports a new processing of the 220 million XP spectra contained in Gaia Data Release 3 (June 2022). In this essay, my main interest is in one of the scientific findings that followed from this data set: the discovery of a new cluster, which they named Ophiion, which has some particularly interesting kinematic properties.

Let me first summarise their revised processing, and provide some background to the wider insights being gained by Gaia for young clusters and associations.

GAIA DR3 includes the mean low-resolution BP/RP spectra (frequently together referred to as the XP spectra) for the brightest 220 million stars (essay 76). Accompanying the spectra were the Gaia Data Processing and Analysis Consortium’s project-level estimates (determined by its Coordination Unit 8) of the astrophysical data for each star, derived from the XP spectra.

I outlined the approach used for these estimates in essay 89. Briefly, the GSP-Phot module within the ‘astrophysical parameters inference system’ (Apsis) provides *model-dependent* estimates of T_{eff} , $\log g$, [M/H], absolute magnitude, radius, distance, line-of-sight extinctions (A_0 , A_G , A_{BP} and A_{RP}) and reddening $E(G_{BP}-G_{RP})$, by forward-modelling the BP/RP spectra, apparent G magnitude, and parallax using a [Markov Chain Monte Carlo](#) method. Details are given by Creevey et al. (2023).

THESE ASTROPHYSICAL data made available with DR3 were never considered to be the final word in classification or parameter estimation. Additional mission data, alongside improvements in calibration, and in training sets and algorithms, were always anticipated.

And indeed, since the release of Gaia DR3, several revised community-generated catalogues of T_{eff} , $\log g$, and [M/H] have been made available, which I described in essay 189. Amongst these are the catalogues of Andrae et al. (2023), Zhang et al. (2023), Khalatyan et al. (2024), Yao et al. (2024), and Hattori (2025).

THE CONTRIBUTION by Huson et al. (2025) uses a new data model, Gaia NET. As detailed in their Section 3, they describe it as a ‘one-dimensional residual convolutional neural network’ based on (SDSS) BOSS Net (Size-more et al., 2024). But the key point they make is that previous parameter determinations from the Gaia XP spectra have been mostly trained on OBAFGK *main-sequence* stars, poorly representing low-mass stars, pre-main sequence stars, and objects below the main sequence (such as hot subdwarfs and white dwarfs).

In contrast, their training set employed a wider spectral range, from SDSS-APOGEE, SDSS-BOSS, and LAMOST. Their goal was to provide a more comprehensive catalogue, covering a wide range of masses and evolutionary stages ($T_{\text{eff}} \sim 2000\text{--}50\,000\text{ K}$, $\log g \sim 0\text{--}10$), with particular attention to pre-main sequence stars. These were, they argue, the first (and only) spectroscopic catalogues providing sufficiently robust estimates of $\log g$ for young stars to enable their use as a proxy for age.

They stress that methods to identify young stars and their ages based on photometry (e.g. using Gaia DR2; McBride et al., 2021) are complicated by the effects of extinction, as well as the contribution from binary systems. From spectroscopy, they argue, estimates of T_{eff} allow the characterisation of sources independently of extinction, while $\log g$ measurements are less biased by binary stars (equal mass binaries producing the same spectroscopic template). And, importantly in this context, given that young stars contract over time, their ages are strongly correlated with $\log g$.

With these results, they then examined the distribution of young low-mass stars with ages $\lesssim 20\text{ Myr}$ in the solar neighbourhood. The sky projection of their selected pre-main sequence candidates is shown over. It correctly traces the known distribution of the nearby star-forming regions, with populations associated with Sco-Cen, Vela, Orion, Perseus, and Cepheus, and many others. In the case of Cepheus, for example, instead of being a monolithic star-forming region, it is seen as several small clouds that are distinct both spatially and kinematically (Szilágyi et al., 2023).

Left: sky projection of pre-main sequence stars, colour-coded by density. Right: zoom-in of the Ophiion region. The overdensity is highlighted by the black polygon, and the circle delineates a ‘bubble’ around ρ Oph. From Huson et al. (2025), Figures 6 and 8.

BEFORE SAYING more on their newly discovered cluster, Ophiion, let me underline a few key points about the progress in characterising young stellar associations and open clusters with Gaia so far.

To summarise the advances being made in the study of open clusters, Gaia’s distances and proper motions are allowing the identification of vastly more clusters than previously known (essay 219), along with rigorous membership and age estimation (essay 220). The motions of *individual* stars allows measurement of their Galactic orbits, as well as details of their dissolution, bulk rotation, and internal dynamics (essay 221).

Concerning young associations (which I reviewed in essay 223), a recurring theme that emerges from the Gaia studies is their spatial complexity. For example, the massive star-forming regions within 600–700 pc (such as Orion, Sco–Cen, and Vela) trace a complex three-dimensional pattern. And cluster analyses often point to structural connections between spatially-separated populations, such as between the Orion Complex and Perseus OB2, and between the sub-regions of Vela.

THE NEAREST and most well-studied association is Scorpius–Centaurus (Sco–Cen, aka Sco OB2), and subgroups including Lower Centaurus Crux and Upper Scorpius. At 130 pc, and extending over 2000 sq. deg., Hipparcos identified over 400 members, while several independent Gaia-based studies have brought the current census to $\sim 15\,000$ (essay 223). And whether associations are expanding or not is linked to the underlying star-formation processes. During their early phases, radiation from hot stars and supernovae can rapidly strip residual gas, although not necessarily resulting in the association’s rapid dispersal. Gaia studies find that many associations are expanding, although others are not.

In their wide-ranging review, Krumholz et al. (2019) concluded that while we now have a broadly satisfying picture, star clusters, which cover a huge range of mass, size, and density scales, ‘*remain mysterious*’.

ADDING TO this mystery, and amongst their identified structures of pre-main sequence stars selected through the use of $\log g$, Huson et al. (2025) drew attention to a population of more than 1000 stars, east of Sco–Cen, and which they named Ophiion. This overdensity had been noted in the Gaia DR3 study of the Sco–Cen OB association by Ratzenböck et al. (2023), who found some 13 000 young co-moving objects organised into 37 co-moving groups (essay 223).

What makes this particular overdensity unusual is that, despite a coherent age of ~ 20 Myr, and at a common distance of ~ 200 pc, it has negligible kinematic coherence. It has a large velocity dispersion $> 20\text{ km s}^{-1}$, without any obvious pattern of expansion. It therefore appears to be fully ‘disrupted’, but at the same time still persisting as a spatial overdensity. Seeing such a massive young population without a coherent core velocity structure is, they argue, somewhat unexpected.

Given the fragmented morphology in this region of Sco–Cen, and the presence of several apparent ‘bubbles’ in the distribution of young stars, they infer that these features were likely driven by one or more supernovae. Their conclusion is that this Ophiion star-forming region lost mass rapidly during the gas-expulsion phase, possibly through a combination of both supernovae and tidal interactions, and resulting in the acceleration of the bulk of the stars to very high velocities.

That the region remains spatially coherent would simply be because it has been caught in the earliest stages of its rapid and complete disruption. Cluster search algorithms relying on both spatial and kinematic coherence would not have found Ophiion!

IFOUND IT interesting that the first three of the five authors of this study are computer scientists, with only one (Logan Sizemore) having another presence on ADS. This nice development perhaps underlines the importance of cross-disciplinary approaches in optimally exploiting the vast Gaia data base.